
Beyond an Unscientific Bias towards a Scientific Knowing for the Authentic Encounter of the Re- ligious Other: A Special Reference to the Thought of Bernard Lonergan

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Abstract: The issues related to engaging with the other, or how to welcome the other, or how we let the other feel friendly in our religious pluralistic environment. Actually this subject is not new but has been dealt with recently in many academic and also practical meetings since the encounter of the other persons would have happened frequently. However, comparatively this issue is not strange to Asians but historically deeply rooted in Asian way of life due to the rich experience of living together as a member of the community beyond the indifferent awareness to the existence of the other in the present times. Borrowing the basic insights of Bernard

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Lonergan, the author explores the unscientific bias towards scientific knowing and encountering the religious other.

In this process, the author transcends a notional or a descriptive apprehension of what we are anticipating or sensing as, now, we move toward apprehensions of meaning that live in an immaterial way within our acts of understanding. That which is not seen and which can never be seen becomes something which is understood through a form of self-transcendence which is endemic to our understanding. It joins us together as we move from a material order of things toward a familiarity that lives with meaning, intelligibility, and spirit towards knowledge societies embracing religious dimension embodied in our contemporary scientific and technological environment.

Keywords: Bernard Lonergan, Religious Other, Scientific Knowledge, Transcendence as faith in human life

Introduction

The general theme of this article is on the issues how to engage with the other, or how to welcome the other, or how we let the other feel friendly in our religious pluralistic environment. Actually this subject is not new but has been dealt with recently in many academic and also practical meetings since the encounter of the other persons would have happened frequently. However, comparatively this issue is not strange to Asians but historically deeply rooted in Asian way of life due to the rich experience of living together as a member of the community beyond the indifferent awareness to the existence of the other in the present times. This experience might be true in many ways in other places of our globe too.

However the general religious perception of the other would be unfortunately emphasized on the negative side of the Western religious world exposing especially violent issues of the crusade or the modern missionary zeal emerging in the context of the

three religious traditions, Judaism, Christianity and Islam. The image is still going on the same track with a strong bias. At the same time unfortunately the usual image is also continuously witnessing the right aspect of them also in the present life in Europe. The positive side of them is not yet communicated for the balancing perception of them in the ordinary level of the modern human life.

The Western and Eastern Approaches to Religion

This is further strengthened in the modern West. Especially when modern “secularism” attempts to deny or eradicate this point, unfortunately a false unscientific bias is conveyed: a bias that faith is not normal in human life, although this kind of diagnosis is both strange and abnormal in the context of global human history. Thus, for the ultimate security of the human life, without a restoration of this point of view in human life, no one can expect that authentic human encounters or fruitful inter-religious dialogue will emerge within the emergent pluralism of our world. Contemporary secular culture does not concern much about our human spiritual security due to disregarding the fundamental principle of transcendence as faith in human life.

In contrast, the perception of the Eastern religious world is quite distinctively intensified in the ideal image in our ordinary way of life. The negative image of the Eastern religious world, especially Hinduism and Buddhism, is not yet deeply engaged with the ordinary way of life. Unfortunately recently the violent image emerging in Hinduism and Buddhism in Asia is reversing the usual ideal image of the two great traditions. Several examples are witnessing this point sharply in the treatment of religious minority groups, the Hindu, the Christian, and the Muslim in Sri Lanka. Also in India and Burma, the treatment of the Christian and the Muslim would be indicated in the similar way. Apart from these examples, so many cases could be pointed out in Asia.

The Religious Other as Minority

In this situation, we could say that the existence of the religious other as a minority in the major dominant religious context would not be easily accepted not only in the West but also in the East. Unlike the ordinary perception of the Hinduism and the Buddhism, the situation of them is not really telling the key difference from the cumulated image of the three religious relationships, especially the Christian and the Muslim. No matter where they would exist, still in our globe, the existence of other as a minority is witnessing the very similar uncomfortable story in the East and the West.

How could we breakthrough individually or collectively this same scheme of recurrence in our globe? Why is it almost impossible to be transformed further for our human good? Where could we find the some clues to break it apart for the new integration of the existence of other for the further friendly community in our globe? Theoretically many studies have already seemingly accomplished for the solution of the problem in religious studies/theologies, philosophies, economics, political science, sociology, psychology, peace and conflict studies, and other modern academic fields.

Nevertheless the problem is recurring repeatedly. Nowadays it is exposing unimaginable extreme situation. The present international institutions such as UN and NATO and various economic associations are not able to interfere and correct it for the creation of the good order of our world. Rather it is going in further extreme way. The speed does not seem to have any break to be stopped. Many criticisms on the religious extreme matters emerging against the other do suggest a good solution but they are not persuasively compelling. Even religious solutions are suggested diversely but the reality is not changed. The problem is further solidly fixed. For example, doctrinally the Hindu and the Buddhist theory of religious other is superb comparing to the Judeo-Christian oriented theory. The former is more theoretically tolerant than the latter. Historically it contributed much broad

perspective in the relation to the religious other. However, in terms of the practice for the religious other, the latter would be seemingly more appealing in modern times about issues of class equality, human right, and gender issues.

Nevertheless, this point could not be totally generalized due to the difference of the various denominations or the different streams of each religious tradition. Still many different aspects could be found in the Judeo-Christian tradition not to welcome the gender issues and also the deeper relationship of the religious other. The opposite aspect of tolerance on this matter could be found in some branches of the Hinduism and the Buddhism. Practically they would reveal the different point as M. K Gandhi and Ven. Thich Nat Han did in their tradition. So in this paper, I would like to approach the matter of the religious other in our pluralistic global times more focusing on the human agent in any activities of our religious life in relation to the other. In so doing, I will not attempt to articulate a doctrinal perspective of the religious other but more emphasize the common anthropological play ground structurally rooted in our human subject as a common foundation for the authentic engagement with the religious other.

Bernard Lonergan's Contributions

In this essay I would like to articulate this issue for the appropriate encounter of the religious other with a special reference to Bernard Lonergan's thought of bias and scientific knowing. Lonergan does not deal intensively with this issue on them in relation to the encounter of the religious other. Nevertheless, I think that his insight could be authentically applied to the encountering context of the religious other in a pluralistic environment emerging more distinctively in our present global times due to the impact of the recent immigration labor market.

Especially, in this occasion I will raise the question of religion and science and we speak about a scientific knowledge of religion or, in other words, about how a scientific understanding of things

can be combined with a religious understanding of the same things. Some kind of fundamental compatibility towards knowledge societies would seem to be possible if we can determine how determinations of meaning in one discipline or perspective have not to be conflict with determinations that belong to another point of view. Both, in some way, exist together.

As a point of departure, two points constitute a suggestive heuristic with respect to the kind of relation which in fact exists between different human groups if we distinguish scientific groups, on the one hand, from religious or literary groups, on the other hand. Our first point refers to a difference (a contrast); our second, a connection with respect to how one kind of knowledge leads to the other.

Scientific Knowledge as Acquired

As our first point, it is to be noted that scientific knowledge exists as acquired knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 149). Its catalyst is the asking of questions as we move from what we know to what we would like to know but have yet to know. None of us are strangers to inquiry. We notice ambiguities. We notice tensions or contradictions. What appears to be may not be and so we ask questions and this asking encourages our moving into philosophic and scientific questions. We can also say that the asking of questions encourages us to move into the possibilities of theological understanding and knowledge although no theological understanding can exist, in any real way, apart from our having some kind of religious faith. In distinguishing the being of any kind of knowledge that comes from questions, we speak about *a posteriori* knowledge or, in more metaphysical terms, *a posteriori* apprehensions of being.

Knowledge as Special intuition

But, on the other hand, the experience of visions is something that is reported to us by many and various persons. It comes to us from testimonies of one kind or another where we encounter

a knowledge of things that does not come from the asking of any questions. In an unsolicited way, a knowledge of things is somehow given to us. It is a kind of knowledge that, in some way, we have prior to the asking of any questions, and because we have not sought or worked to have this kind of knowledge, we speak about a kind of knowledge which, in its immediacy, is best described as a species of intuition. It exists as a kind of unmerited gift and, on our side, if we attend to the quality of our subjectivity, we best speak about a receptivity that is purely open and submissive. In this kind of knowledge, we have an *a priori* kind of knowledge or, in more metaphysical terms, an *a priori* apprehension of being (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 145-158).

Turning to point two, in examining the order of our human knowledge, we find that *a priori* kinds of knowledge precede *a posteriori* kinds of knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 16). If our acquired knowledge of things always move from a knowledge and an understanding of things that we already have and we do not have to acquire it, then, inevitably, we are forced to admit that all acquired knowledge and its acquisition is predicated on the basis of a more primitive, basic kind of knowledge as this exists for us as a kind of gift that comes to us from sources that we might not exactly know or understand. In other words, if we turn our attention of a larger study of *a priori* kinds of knowledge, we discover foundations for scientific and philosophic knowledge that can be traced to the reality and the being of literary and religious roots. If we should refer to the seeing of any visions in a literary or religious context, we refer to condensed, compact apprehensions of meaning and being which have yet to be fully understood. Symbolic apprehensions of meaning and being precede scientific apprehensions of meaning and being and, if we retain this focus and realize its importance, we can begin to understand why literary and religious apprehensions of meaning and being have an importance that is crucial for us as human beings. We begin with these and if we are working with apprehensions of meaning and being which are provocative and

suggestive, we can move into the kind of meaning as this exists emerges in the practice of religion and science.

Concluding Suggestion

Furthermore, I would like to point to the fruitfulness of a larger framework which can be identified if we should raise questions about how or why the growth which exists in our human knowledge of things is something that can be joined to the kind of knowledge which exists if we should refer to a second kind of familiarity or a second kind of knowledge which exists for us through the human experience of visions that can be found if we should refer to how, in various literary or religious contexts, persons sometimes speak about a different kind of seeing that mysteriously belongs to them. It differs from the kind of seeing which belongs to their ordinary or common knowledge of things and it also differs from the kind of seeing which belongs to a scientific seeing of things that belongs to the genesis and the growth of scientific knowledge (Lonergan Institute, 2019: 152-154).

In other words, we transcend a notional or a descriptive apprehension of what we are anticipating or sensing as, now, we move toward apprehensions of meaning that live in an immaterial way within our acts of understanding. That which is not seen and which can never be seen becomes something which is understood through a form of self-transcendence which is endemic to our understanding. It joins us together as we move from a material order of things toward a familiarity that lives with meaning, intelligibility, and spirit towards knowledge societies embracing religious dimension embodied in our contemporary scientific and technological environment.

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